

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PARENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN SOKOTO METROPOLIS NIGERIA

Nasiru Abubakar Katami

Sokoto State University, Sokoto

e-mail: katami2012@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper analyzed the impact of parent's socio-economic background on the academic performance of the students in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto state of Nigeria. There are two objectives, research questions and hypotheses that guided the study. In order to carry out the research, data collected from 350 respondents out of the 4466 students of the schools in Sokoto metropolis, using simple random sampling technique. Questionnaires were administered to the respondents and data collected was analyzed using regression analysis. The results shows that parent's socio-economic class; fathers' level of education and mothers' level of education are the major determinants of the academic performance of students in Sokoto metropolis. The research recommends a vibrant poverty alleviation program for poor parents in Sokoto state.

Keywords: Impact, Parents, Socio-economic Background, Academic performance

Introduction

The family is the major agent of molding the child to the form desired. It plays indispensable roles in continuity of generations that enhances sustainability of society. Family is the core of the society and whatever the family is, that is what the society is. It is along this premise that (Awoju, 2007) argues that the entire atmosphere as created by parents would to a large extent determine how well adjusted a child that comes from such family would be. This is because the fact remains that the child's ability to comport himself/herself, solve and execute tasks in life depends on how the individual has been handled while young.

The family has influence on the academic performances of the child even before the advent of formal education in Nigeria. Salafani (2004) claims, that family is the best factory where the child is processed to learn about the norms, values, culture, aspirations and the desires of the society. This underscores why the family has profound influence on the evaluative aspects of the child's development including his academic achievement. A child desires his satisfaction and dissatisfaction and his sense of values are influenced by the educational statuses in the family too.

As the family is the social group with which the child has direct contact, it determines not only the individual's personality but also his academic performance at least to some appreciable extent. A child is raised in accordance with the values of the family and as he grows, he learns, internalizes and concretizes the behavioral patterns and training which the child learns from the family often determines his academic performance and subsequent achievement.

The socio-economic factors have a tremendous influence on students' academic performance. According to Oguntoye (1982), educational resources are people, places, events and materials that can be used for enhancing human learning in any field of specialization or form of knowledge or those things that have the capacity for simplifying or improving the learnability of a given subject matter such as television set, pictures, diagrams, charts, the subject teachers and resources persons outside the school.

However, majority of the parents fall below poverty line, Ijarya (2000). The dwindling income have far reached implication for people's or parents' ability to invest in qualitative education of their children and thus, affects students' academic performance. This is because students from low-income earners, whose income can only sustain them in their inevitable needs, find it difficult to send their children to good or qualitative schools where they can receive qualitative learning. And as a result, when compared such children with their counterparts, their academic performance lack behind. When one considers the tempo of juvenile delinquency, anomie and ignorance or wrong attitude towards academic activities, one can conclude that some families' position leaves much to be desired. Most of the factors responsible for the above vices includes inability of parents to supply the needs of their children, improper handling of children and failure of family to mentor the academic activities of their children. Furthermore, Okujagu cited in Salafani (2004) reported other family background factors that have considerable effects on a child's attainment at parental level of education, family size, birth order position, home environment, etc.

According to Okujagu in Selafani (2004), parental education has more important impact on children's academic performance in the overall context of socio-economic background. Studies by Enoh (2003), have shown that children are more likely to do well academically if their parent or guardian had some form of formal education than if they had none. This is because parents with some forms of formal education are more motivating and have higher achievement aspiration. They are more prone to be aware of the benefits and importance of education and as such more likely to support and encourage or motivate their children to study. According to Douglas (1994) the more highly parents value education the more they will support their children's educational endeavors and the more highly they will succeed. On the other hand, parents with no form of formal education may not be aware of the symbolic value of education and are also not in the position to help their children learn at home. Thus, children from uneducated parents tend to be unsupervised in their activities and are allowed a great deal of unorganized freedom (Okujagu in Salafani, 2004). Fan (2001) demonstrated that parents' educational aspiration for their children proved to be strongly related to students' academic growth. Research studies have found that parental educational level has a significant impact on child's learning, (Khan, and Malik, 1997). Similarly, Schneider and Lee (1990) linked the academic success of the East Asian students to the values and aspirations they share with their parents, and also to the home learning activities in which their parents involved with their parents, and also to the home learning activities in which their parents involve with them. In fact, all parents have desired to do something better for their children according to their available resources. But the extent and effectiveness of parental support depends on a variety of resources, such as, ethnicity, family income, and home environment and their awareness about the importance of education.

Thus, parental level of education and occupations such as teaching may have more influence on children academic achievement.

Simiyu cited in Charles (2013) argues that the family income refers to wages, salaries, profit, rent and any other flow of earnings received. Income can also come in the form unemployment or workers compensation, social security, pensions, interest or dividend, royalties, trust, alimony or other governmental public or family financial assistance.

In general, educational outcomes have been shown to be influenced by family background in many different and complex ways. Saha cited in Wolframs (2005) for example, the socio-economic status of families has been constantly found to be an important variable in explaining variance in student achievement. Socio-economic background may affect learning outcomes in numerous ways: From the onset, parents with higher socio-economic status are able to provide their children with the often-necessary financial support and home resources for individual learning. They are also more likely to provide a more stimulating home environment to promote cognitive development.

The relationship between family socio-economic background and the academic performance of children is well established in sociological researches. While there is a disagreement over how best to measure socio-economic status, most studies indicate that children from low socio-economic families do not perform as well as they potentially could at school compared to children from high socio-economic status families. Grith (2004). Most studies however, compare students from across all socio-economic background to reach the conclusion that low socio-economic status adversely affects a range of educational outcomes.

Sokoto State is one of the backward states in education in Nigeria according to the report of the National Bureau of Statistics 2012. Therefore, investigating any activity that may likely promote the performance of students in school is important. Many reaches on students' educational performance were conducted in Sokoto state but to the best of the knowledge of the researcher not single research was conducted on the impact of parent's socio-economic background on student academic performance, that includes the level of education of both the father and mother of separate variables. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to analyze the impact of parents' socio-economic background on secondary school students' academic performance in Sokoto metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

This study intends to examine if there is any:

1. Relationship between family socio-economic class and academic performance of students in Sokoto metropolis
2. The relationship between fathers' level of education and student academic performance in Sokoto metropolis
3. The relationship between students' academic performance and mothers' level of education in Sokoto metropolis

Research Hypothesis

In an attempt to provide answers to the research question stated above, the following hypotheses were tested.

1. There is no significant relationship between family socio-economic background and academic performance of the students in Sokoto metropolis

Review of Related Literature

The review of related literature includes the following areas. They are the conceptual framework, theoretical framework and empirical literature.

Concept of Socio-economic Background

Socio-economic status refers to the position of individuals, families, household or other aggregates on one or more dimension of stratification. These dimensions according to UNESCO (1992) include income, education, prestige, wealth or other aspect of standing those members of society deem salient. There are different ideas about what class is, but it is generally defined relationally, referring to groups of people who share a similar position, such as the relationship to the means of production. All too often, socio-economic status and class are ambiguous terms that serve as shorthand expression to refer to social and economic characteristics that are believed to be important, but the rationale or meaning of which is always made clear.

There are nearly as many concepts of socio-economic status and class as there are authors writing on them. However, it is possible to discern two broad approaches. The first sees class or socio-economic status (SES) as essentially a unitary concept. From these perspectives, a fundamental dimension underlies class (or SES), and it is this that is the primary driving force of some class analysis. The second viewpoint focuses on the components of socio-economic status (SES) or class and treats them as having distinct effects UNESCO (1992). This conceptualization disputes the unidirectionality of class or socio-economic status (SES). It highlights the separate dimensions of stratification and predicts that different dimensions can have different consequences.

Concept of Academic Performance

This is the attainment of educational goals by a student, teacher or institution achievement over a certain period. It is measured either by examination or continuous assessment and the goals may differ from an individual or institution to another. Academic performance also can be defined as excellence in all academic disciplines, in class as well as extra-curricular activities. It includes excellence in sporting, behavior, confidence, communication skills, punctuality, assertiveness, arts, culture and the like.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

In a study on family background, educational achievement and occupational aspirations among secondary school students in Ondo state, Daramola (1997) found that there is a significant relationship among family background, parental control and academic achievement of the pupils. The finding is also similar to that of Khan and Zubairi (1999) where they found that parental educational level and socio-economic status has a significant impact on child's learning.

In a study on the influence of parents' educational background and study facilities on Academic performance among secondary school students Funmi Lola *et al* (2013) found

that educational background of parents and provision of study facilities for children at home have significant influence on the academic performance of such children. The finding is also similar to that of Musarat *et al* (2013) where they found that parental education and socio-economic status of parents have momentous effects on students' academic achievement at master's level. The above findings are supported by various researches one of which is by Hanes (2008) where he carried out research on factors affecting students' academic performance and come up with the result that "higher level of socio- economic status is the best indicator towards the quality of students' achievement".

In another study on the analysis and interpretation of data by Memons *et al* (2010) found that students whose parents are well educated perform better than those students whose parents are less educated. He further stated that the higher the income of family, better would be students availability of resources and consequently better would be academic achievements. On the contrary Adewale (2012) investigated and showed that educational background and socio-economic are not much important influencing factors in students' academic performance.

Methodology

The methodology of this research work includes research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling techniques, instrumentation, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

Research Design

A sample survey method was adopted for this study. Sample survey is an investigation in which only part or sample of the population is studied and the selection is made such that the sample is the representative of the whole population. It is a kind of study in which a random sample is taken from a well-defined population, data is collected from the sample, statistic is calculated from the data and the statistic is used to estimate the true value in the population.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all SS students of Senior Day Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis which is 4466, as shown in table 1:

Table 1: Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto Metropolis

S/No.	School	No. of Hausa students	No. of Yoroba students	Total
1.	A.A. Raji SP School Sokoto	251	138	389
2	ADSS Sokoto	234	151	385
3	GDSS Gidan – Igwai	232	105	337
4	GDSS KofarMarke	168	64	232
5	GDSS KofarRini	343	119	462
6	GDSS Mabera	553	299	762
7	GDSS Runjin Sambo	441	209	643
8	GDSS Arkilla	298	159	457

9	GDSS Tudun Wada Sokoto	279	137	416
10	GGASS Sabon Birni (Sokoto North)	248	41	289
11	GGASS Yar' Akija	247	-	247
12	GMSS Sokoto	327	131	458
13	HABMASS Sokoto	357	132	489
14	NGSS Sokoto	391	252	643
15	SAASS Sokoto	198	101	299
16	SAC Sokoto	507	113	620
17	SAGMC Sokoto	171	41	212
18	SASS Sokoto	231	117	348
19	SBSS Sokoto	281	142	423
20	SDUSS Farfaru	212	110	322
21	SSC Sokoto	337	98	435
22	WCCE Sokoto	187	52	239

Source: Ministry of Education, Sokoto – Examination Unit (2019) Promotion/Repeating Examination.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample of three hundred and fifty students were selected for the study.

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire developed by the researcher which was validated by some of the lecturers from Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto was used in collecting data. The instrument was found reliable. The questions were asked on respondent's parent's educational qualification and respondent's parent's educational status.

Method of Data Analysis

In analyzing the data correlation Pearson 'r' was used to test the relationship between the parent's socio-economic background and student's academic performance. Also, frequency counts and percentage were used on respondent's demographic data.

Model Specification

The following model was developed for the research:

$$SAP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FEQ + \beta_2 MEQ + \beta_3 PSC + E$$

Where: SAP stand for students' Academic Performance

B1 stands for Father's educational qualification

B2 stands for Mothers educational qualification

B3 stands for Parents Socio-economic class

Results and Discussions

The result is categorized into two; the descriptive statistic result that analyze the personal and demographic characteristics of the responding students and regression result, that test the research hypothesis.

The results shows that 164 (51.25%) are male while 156(48.75%) are female, also about 216(67.4%) of the respondents are Hausa as against Yoruba's that are 104(32.6%). On the respondent's father's education. The result also indicates that 102(31.8%) of the

respondent's fathers are SSCE holders, 70(22.3%) are degree holders. 58(18.3%) are holders of NCE and equivalent and primary certificate holders are 46(14.9%) and Master's degree holders are only 16(5.11%) of the population. Further more 129(31%) of the respondent's fathers' occupations are traders as against 80(24.7%) that are civil servants. 48(15.13%) of them are farmers, 39(12.18%) are teachers and only 15(5%) are politicians. The result also shows that 97(30.4%) of the respondent's mothers poses only religious education qualification as against 80(24.9) that are SSCE holders. Further more the result shows that 61(10.05%) are primary certificate holders. NCE and equivalent constitutes 56(17.6%).

Hypothesis Testing

The Hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between parental socio-economic background and academic performance of students in Sokoto metropolis.

Table 2: Pearson 'r' showing Result on Relationship between family socio-economic background and academic performance of Students in Sokoto metropolis

Variables	No	Mean	Std	Df	Cal	r-value	p-value	Remark
Academic Performance	320	35.09	15.423	318	0.715	0.715	3.560	Ho rejected
Socio-economic status	320	1.65	.693					

Source: Computed from field survey data, 2019

The table above shows that the calculated r-value is 0.715 while the critical r-value is 0.088 with 318 degree of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance. Since the calculated r-value is greater than the critical value, therefore the hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. That there is a positive significance relationship between the parental socio-economic background and academic performance of students in Sokoto metropolis. The result highlights the importance of socio-economic class as a major determinant of academic performance.

Discussion

Parental socio-economic background is based on family income, parental educational level, parental occupation and social status in the community. The research found a significantly positive relationship between parental socio-economic background and students' academic performance in Sokoto metropolis. This is in agreement with the earlier findings by Ezewa (1977), Frazer (1983) and Bichi (1996). Ezewa conducted his research in Lagos, Frazer (1983) conducted his research on secondary school students Bichi (1996) conducted his research in kano. Since the researches in both Northern and Western parts of Nigeria and the result indicates that there is a significant relationship between socio-economic background and academic performance of students. In another study conducted by Miner (1986) in United State quoted in Uche (1986) which aimed at identifying some of the sociological variables affecting school achievement, found that socio-economic background of the child was related to the level of achievement attained.

Conclusion

From the findings above we can conclude that parental socio-economic background is a major determinant of student's academic performance in Sokoto metropolis of Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Informed by the finding of this study, it is the recommendation of the author that:

1. Government should implement poverty alleviation program honestly so as to improve the economic standard of poor parents so that they can afford to send their children to school and provide them with needed learning materials.
2. Teachers should have a balance understanding of the uniqueness that exist among their students in terms of their socio-economic background and the differences in general and specific abilities so that they can blend their method of teaching in such a way that all students benefit equally.

References

- Adewale, (2012). Parental educational Aspiration and Children's Performance in Funtua Area of Kaduna State. M. Sc. Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Akpochafor, M. B. (1985). Socialisation and the parent – child Relationship, *Child Development*, **19**: 127 – 136.
- Douglas, J. W. P. (1994). The Home and School. London, Mac Gibson and Kee.
- Ezewu, E. E. (1977). Relationship between Social Positions and Academic Achievement within Classroom groups. Sociology of Education, Lagos: Longman Nigeria Ltd.
- Enoh, A. O. (2003). Elements of Education and Society. Fab Amech Ltd.
- Fan, X. (2001). Parental involvement and students' Academic Achievement: A Growth Modelling Analysis. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, **70** (1): 27 – 61.
- Funmilola *et al* (2013). "Influence of Family and School Variables on Secondary School students' academic achievement in Kwara State, Nigeria". Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, University of Ilorin.
- Grith, D. K. (2004). Family Structure and Children Educational attainment, the Heritage Foundation, Washington, DC: 214 Massachusetts Avenue M. E.
- Hanes, (2008). "Socio-Economic Variables, Determinants of Academic Performance in Nigerian Universities". Unpublished Research paper, Human Resources Centre, University of Lagos.
- Khan, R. M., Khan, M. A. and Zubairi, N. (1999). Parental Involvement and Reading Attainment: A Study of 4th Grade Pakistani Children, *Journal Pendidikan*, **20**: 83 – 94; Fakulti Pedidikan University, Malaya.
- Krejecie, R. and Morgan, D. W. (1970). "Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, **30**.
- Muhammad, R. (2007). "The Relationship between self-concept, Family Background and Academic Achievement among Female Science Secondary School Students in Sokoto", unpublished PhD. Thesis, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
- Pamela, E. & Kean, V. (2005). The influence of parents' education and family income on child achievement: The indirect role of parental expectations and the home environment. *Journal of Family Psychology*, **19** (2): 294 – 304.
-

- Oguntoye, A. O. (1982). Input, Output analysis in a Nigerian Secondary School system, Saha cited in Walframs (2005) Parents Involvement in the Home, School and Community Colorado West View Press.
- Salafani, J. D. (2004). The educated parent: recent trends in raising children. Connecticut: Praeger Publishers.
- Sambo, A. A. (2008). Research method in education. Ibadan: Stirling Horden Publishers (Nig.) Ltd.
- Schneider, B. and Lee, Y. (1990). A Model for Academic success: The School and Home Environment of East Asia students. *Anthropology and Education Quarterly*, **21** (4): 358 – 377.
- Suresh, K. N. V. (2010). Parental Involvement in children's Education: Does parents' Education level really Matters? *European Journal of Social Sciences*, **16** (3): 430 – 445.
- UNESCO – IIEP (1992). Increasing and improving the quality of basic education. International Institute of Educational Planning, UNESCO, Paris.